

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Foreign Language Textbook for Teaching Atypical Students: Designing Didactic Materials

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Abstract

The article considers the need to develop author's didactic materials as applications to modern foreign language textbooks, which is associated with the difficulty of creating a universal textbook taking into account the specifics of the limitations of a schoolchild who has problems in socialization, learning, development and education. The article highlights the peculiarity of preparing a future foreign language teacher for designing didactic support for sections of a foreign language textbook within university elective courses.

The leading methods to study the problem of designing didactic support for atypical students are: 1) theoretical methods: analysis of psychological, pedagogical, methodological works of foreign and Russian authors on the problem under review, comparison, generalization, design, modeling, interpretation of the information received; 2) empirical methods: observation, testing, questionnaires, conversation with students, research of future Bachelors of Education project results; 3) methods of mathematical statistics (Microsoft Office Excel 2010).

The scientific novelty lies in the justification of the didactic functions of provision for atypical students, establishing theoretical basis for the model of designing didactic support based on the principle of personalized learning as a gradual transfer of a student to the position of self-learner.

The practical significance of the study results presented in the article lies in the development of a model for the design of didactic support for atypical students, the allocation of a step-by-step algorithm for this process, the development of elective courses and modular disciplines, in the creation of a training manual "Teacher's readiness to develop Individual Educational Plan for schoolchildren".

Keywords: specialized skills, author's didactic materials for textbooks.

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Introduction

The relevance of the problem. Teaching an atypical student at the present stage of the development of education is related to the formation of an inclusive foreign-language education field, which requires the search for innovative methods and ways to reconsider the role of the textbook as a means of reflecting the latest educational trends in the personification and differentiation of learning. The latter is commonly included in the official documents – the guidelines of educational institutions and curricular. The large scale of the disability problem determines the need for the state to take a set of measures to organize a system of social protection and social integration of children with disabilities. Atypical personality, considered as a complex of various deviations, is a kind of life situation, which is characterized by the severity of different degrees of interaction of the student with society and insufficiency, which are determined by the influence of biological and social factors (Mel'nik, 2019, p. 45).

The presence of individual positive or negative deviations from the generally accepted norm (belonging to an ethnic, linguistic, cultural, religious minority, a natural aptitude, health problems, etc.), as well as age restrictions inherent in school age, lead to partial or complete isolation of an atypical child from society (Staritsyna, 2018, p. 275).

The concept of inclusive education provides an opportunity for children with disabilities to “get involved” in the life of society. Federal Law No. 273-FZ “On Education in the Russian Federation” guarantees equal access to education for all students, taking into account the diversity of special educational needs and individual opportunities (Federal Law No. 273-FZ).

In modern society, inclusive education means the co-education of students with disabilities and peers with normative development. The ideology of inclusive education is that in order to attain high-quality education, to socialize and to adopt in society, it is important for children with special needs to actively interact with other children. For students with disabilities, a positive consequence of such communication is the possibility of co-developing, co-educating, attending a mainstream classroom, and enjoying friendly relationships with fellow “ordinary” learners. The dominating ideal theories of inclusive education state that students with disabilities shall be entitled to full membership in regular classes together with children from the same neighbourhood in local schools. There they should have access to differentiated and individualized support, programs and assessments. Inclusive education then means to teach all students

together in a normal school-class setting, where they all receive teaching that corresponds to their abilities and interests (Haug, 2017, p. 208).

Foreign language as a discipline is actively studied in educational institutions of different levels - from preschool to postgraduate. Due to the heterogeneity of the composition of students, their abilities, the nature of perception and assimilation of the material being studied, teaching a foreign language requires a personalized approach (Teacher Education, 2016).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The current work aims at justifying the need to develop specialized methodological skills of future teachers to design a variety of didactic materials for support of atypical schoolchildren in personalized foreign language teaching. The authors emphasize that the differentiated didactic support for students, taking into account the specifics of their inclusion, is an effective means of improving the quality of teaching a foreign language, with regard to the functions of the presented educational tasks, exercises, and texts. The purpose of the study was implemented in the following objectives:

- 1) to characterize the modern trends in personalized teaching and educating students;
- 2) to analyze scientific, pedagogical and methodological literature and identify the specialized skills of a teacher to design didactic support for atypical students within the framework of personified learning;
- 3) to develop the stages of empirical research of specialized teacher skills' formation within the framework of university-wide elective and modular courses;
- 4) to test the results obtained at scientific and practical conferences, webinars, master classes, in the process of volunteering.

Literature review

The analysis of the currently existing works from pedagogical and methodological publications allows us to conclude that scientists have already considered the following issues: problems of individualization and differentiation of foreign language vocational education (Podymova, Galskova, Pribylova, Shamanova and others); development of individual strategies for educating, students' support, autonomy of learning (Sorokovykh and others), creating an inclusive foreign language environment and teaching atypical students (Sorokovykh, Mel'nik, Staritsyna, etc.), learning in the context of intercultural communication

(Tareva, Byram, etc.).

Modern trends in personalized learning and education of atypical students are revealed in the following dimensions:

- **humanization of education**, which sets the task of improving the general intellectual and cultural level of students, the implementation of integration processes in education; application of methods, techniques, pace of learning, with regard to personal characteristics and educational needs of the individual and the level of development of abilities for learning;

- **the integrity of training and education** in an inclusive field is associated with the upbringing of such an important quality for our society as tolerance; acceptance of the person's individuality with his characteristics and abilities; development of respect for a person with different abilities and qualities; understanding the restrictions of other people; the formation of responsibility, respect for the rights of others; mutual help, empathy; development of identity as the basis for tolerant attitude towards others.

- **informatization** is a strategic task of creating personalized e-learning environment of an educational organization transferring a student to the position of a learning subject that involves creation of individual routes of training and education, increasing importance of the levels of differentiation that contributes to the successful overcoming of difficulties in social adaptation and stimulates further development;

- **democratization of education** is linked to the creation of prerequisites for enhancing cognitive activity, development of critical thinking and student initiative based on the design and development of various interactive technologies. It is also important to mention granting the right to choose both programs and educational organizations based on the principle of differentiation and individualization of training and education. Personalized education of atypical students is aimed at the development of reflexive thinking as a controlling mechanism of a person in life;

- **individualization of training and education**, which implies the use of the modular principle of implementation of adapted educational programs and provides flexibility and accessibility of the development of educational material in accordance with the needs and abilities of students. Thus, the system of tasks offered to an atypical student should meet the pace of entry into the content of the subject, the level of proficiency in the subject (s), the cognitive capabilities of an atypical student. Individualization of learning is aimed at overcoming the contradictions between the level of educational activity that the programs set and the real capabilities of each subject of the educational process.

Methodology

Theoretical analysis of psychological, pedagogical and methodological works of foreign and Russian researchers demonstrated the leading role of technological and competence-based approaches in the development of this problem (M. V. Klarin, G. Dudney). M. V. Klarin defines pedagogical technology as “the system set and the order of functioning of all personal, instrumental and methodological tools used to achieve pedagogical goals” (Klarin, 2016). This includes not just ‘technical’ skills, but perhaps more importantly, an awareness of the social practices that surround the appropriate use of new technologies (Dudney, 2016, p.115).

The implementation of the technological approach in our study is characterized by a step-by-step solution of problems: the formation of a theoretical and scientific-methodological and research bases; planning and designing work in accordance with the specifics of teaching a foreign language to atypical students; optimal use of information and communication technologies (ICT) and didactic resources in the educational process and providing students with competent consistent scientific and pedagogical guidance of their use in inclusive teaching of a foreign language.

The humanistic approach as a category of personalized learning has significant importance for the formation of the projective skills of future teachers. By the humanistic approach we understand the organization of the educational process, which aims at self-actualization of the individual and involves the formation of self-learning mechanisms through the satisfaction of his basic needs: in psychologically friendly interpersonal relationships and social status; in the realization of its creative potential, in the learning process in accordance with his or her individual cognitive strategies (Pribylova, 2019, p.329).

The development of Russian statehood and civil society are taking place in the new social and historical conditions which require to rethink of the place and role of education as a sphere of preservation and reproduction of national and cultural values. As E.G. Tareva emphasizes, “the national mentality, national culture, moral character of a person, who is a bearer of national identity, should become the main value of the state” (Tareva, 2017 p. 20). Values always have regulated and determined the meanings of life, the importance and significance of something personal for a person. Axiological points have always been the essential basis of personality. A foreign language, acting, on the one hand, as a means of forming and developing a student’s personality, and, on the other, as a means of learning a different culture, in its turn acquires the status of social value (Samohin, 2018, p. 24).

We should primarily attribute to axiological values of the new paradigm of education the changing attitude to the personality of a student and a teacher, and not only in the context of interacting agents engaged in

foreign educational activities, but also awareness of the importance of the intrinsic value of the individual, accepting his uniqueness, the importance of creating conditions for personal development for a student and a teacher. (Vorob'eva, 2016, p. 107).

Results

We carried out an experimental study consisting of three stages. At the first, **observation stage**, the main goal was to determine the initial level of all parameters and factors to be monitored during the experiment. In order to identify the level of didactic competence of bachelors, we conducted a survey, including 3 groups of questions:

- 1) issues related to the general awareness of inclusive education as a form of organization of school training;
- 2) questions that help assess the readiness of future teachers to work with atypical students;
- 3) questions assessing the level of methodological competence of specialists, their knowledge of methods of teaching a foreign language to atypical students.

The survey revealed the lack of any current knowledge and skills that prepare future teachers to interact with atypical students. Moreover, the respondents have indicated that there are no specific sources of information or modules in the curriculum introducing them to work in an inclusive environment.

The practical experience of training future teachers to teach and educate in the context of a personified foreign language education, surveys and one-to-one interviews with school teachers in the framework of webinars showed that in order to design didactic support for atypical students successfully, bachelors must master the following skills:

- the ability to identify the special educational needs of atypical students in mastering foreign language communicative competence;
- the ability to design an adaptive module in a foreign language, aimed at reducing the impact of health restrictions in the formation of foreign language communicative competence of students at various stages of language education;
- the ability to prepare didactic materials and use modern educational technologies, special language and speech compensatory techniques of delivering materials to atypical schoolchildren;

- master the techniques of designing assessment materials for language and culture education, methods of their presentation based on the humanistic principle of acceptance of the atypical students' language skills results by normative-developing peers;

An important task of the experimental study of the problem of teacher preparation for the design of didactic support for atypical schoolchildren for our study was the stage of developing a theoretical model.

Through modeling, the pedagogical process is represented as a system that includes such elements as the goal, objectives, content, approaches, principles, components, stages, forms, methods, technologies, criteria, indicators, levels, pedagogical conditions, results. Modeling as a social research method allows us to take into account the system of major factors, conditions, and provisions that affect the content of the model, its levels of development and structure, and to identify of its components. The structural components of our model (Fig. 1) reveal the organization of didactic support for atypical students in the framework of personalized foreign language teaching, such as the purpose, objectives, approaches, principles, forms, methods, technologies and means of individualization and differentiation of learning, tools for comprehensive assessment. The abovementioned components are responsible for the constant flow of interaction between the constituent elements of this process.

Figure 01. The model of formation of specialized skills

In this model we can see that the specifics of didactic support of atypical schoolchildren consist of the following elements: justifying the idea within the target component, creation of personalized environment (methodological and content components), implementation of interactive methods of teaching and educating students with SEN based on the designed didactic support (technological component), analysis of the results obtained and reflection (reflexive components).

The purpose of the second stage was to conduct a formative experiment on the development of design

competencies of the second and third year bachelors majoring in pedagogy.

The formative experiment included the following components:

- 1) implementation of elective modules;
- 2) delivering conferences and master classes, webinars for Moscow teachers, etc.
- 3) publication of a textbook, which examines the important issues of preparing a modern teacher to design individual routes of training and education, taking into account the specific needs and capabilities of students based on scientific analysis and practical experience. The main aim of individual programs is to help students start moving independently in those areas where they are ready to progress, constantly expanding their horizons and focusing on a broad adaptation of the individual to social requirements and living conditions (Sorokovykh, Pribylova, Staritsyna, 2020, p. 8).
- 4) volunteer work of bachelors of pedagogical specialties with atypical students in the Maintained boarding school №1 for visually impaired children, workshop “Svetoch”.

We have developed and implemented university elective courses within the framework of the module “The teacher’s readiness to design Individual Educational Plan”. The first discipline of the module “Studying the personality of a child with SEN” was aimed at developing in future teachers a system of pedagogical knowledge, skills and abilities to choose an Individual Educational Plan depending on the age and individual characteristics of a child with special educational needs. During the course, the students studied in detail the special conditions for inclusive education of various groups of atypical students and prepared fragments of a foreign language lesson’s content in conditions of inclusion. The second discipline of the module “Technology for design of adaptive programs” aimed at teaching Bachelors of Education to model individual educational plan for children at primary and secondary schools. The aspects of the tutor’s work in the context of personalized foreign language teaching were considered within the third discipline “Tutor support for the formation of readiness for self-education”. As a result, the students have prepared didactic support for teaching languages in primary and secondary schools.

The developed programs of elective courses and modular disciplines have been tested for two years, the content of these programs is briefly presented in the summary Table 01.

Table 01. Content and didactic stages of the implementation of an experimental study on the formation of specialized skills of a teacher to design didactic support for an atypical student in personalized learning

Name of the elective course or module	Types and forms of interactive methods for the formation of specialized skills to design didactic support		
	Observation	Testing	Generalization
Studying the personality of a child with SEN	Survey to identify the level of development of didactic competence of Bachelors	Interactive lectures, master classes and round table discussions aimed at developing the ability of future teachers to choose an Individual Education Plan, regarding individual characteristics of atypical students	Preparing a fragment of a foreign language lesson in inclusive learning; preparation of practical guidelines for teachers on the design of didactic support for atypical schoolchildren in personalized foreign language teaching
Tutor support for the formation of readiness for self-education	Tutor - an organizer of programs with cultural institutions ('road map' of social and leisure activities). An essay "If I were a tutor"	Developing sample models of a tutor's activity	Developing an Individual Education Plan of learning and upbringing for an atypical student
Technology for design of adaptive programs	Research "Development and updating educational material for students with different levels of knowledge of foreign languages via ICT"	Tutorials: "Formation and development of readiness of a foreign language teacher to design adaptive programs in the educational environment using IT"	"Defending an individual project on the adaptive program of educating atypical school children". Designing an advertisement and a multimedia presentation
Pedagogical conflict within the triad 'pupil-teacher-parent'	Psychological and pedagogical research of a problem student. Preparation of surveys	Case-study (examples of conflicts at school, determination of their object and subject, handling incidents that provoked them	Research project: The cause of interpersonal conflict

Readiness to design an Individual Educational Plan	Developing the lesson structure with the outline of the elements providing for the use of ICT in a differentiated approach	Tutorials: “Developing and describing an explanatory note to the adaptive educational program on the subject, which should present the terms of mastering the program, tasks and goals, as well as the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of students”	Designing an Individual Education Plan of self-study for a student with disabilities. Preparing a presentation
Pedagogical mastery of communication	Self-diagnosis of personal qualities in the structure of methodological competence of a foreign language teacher	Discussion “Professional gaffs of a teacher”	Developing a script for a parent meeting about the problems of socialization at school

In this table we can see that the use of various interactive forms of teacher-student interaction contributes to the effective methodological preparation of the teacher to design of the educational system, considering the different levels of students (Sorokovykh, Pribylova, Staritsyna, 2020, p. 31).

A significant contribution to the implementation of the experiment was made by testing students’ materials within practice-oriented master classes. At the generalization stage, together with the students, practical recommendations were developed for the design of didactic support for atypical schoolchildren in personalized foreign language teaching, among which the need to implement an individual and differentiated approaches were a strategic task.

Let us clarify that 194 students and 5 teachers of the Moscow City University took part in the experimental study. The conclusion of the level of building the teacher’s specialized skills to design didactic support for students with problems in learning, development and upbringing was based on the results of completing the tasks.

Having described the level characteristic of the formation of specialized skills to design didactic support for atypical schoolchildren through analysis, observation and testing, we concluded, that the optimal number of level categories can be represented in the form of the following classification:

- elementary;
- intermediate;
- advanced.

We have outlined the characteristics of these levels in Table 02.

Table 02. Characteristics of the levels of formation of specialized skills of a teacher to design didactic support for atypical students while teaching a foreign language

The level of mastery of specialized skills	Characteristics of the level of formation of specialized skills
Advanced	The student: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - can identify the SEN of atypical students in mastering foreign language communicative competence; - has the skills of designing an adaptative module in a foreign language, aimed at reducing the impact of health restrictions in the formation of foreign-language communicative competence of schoolchildren at various stages of language education; - can prepare didactic materials and use modern educational technologies, special methods and techniques of compensatory presentation of language and speech materials of the lesson for atypical students; - knows the techniques of designing assessment materials for language and culture education, methods of their presentation based on the humanistic principle of acceptance by normal peers of the results of the formation of language skills and the development of speech skills of atypical children (Sorokovykh, Zharkova, 2020, p. 183).
Intermediate	The student is ready to perform the functions as part of the advanced level, but has difficulties in making decisions and needs advice from the teacher
Elementary	The student has not sufficiently mastered the knowledge, skills and methods of design, he needs consultations and performs all actions at the level of reproductive tasks

The process of building specialized skills can be represented in the form of a diagram.

Figure 02. The dynamics of the formation of teacher's specialized skills to design didactic support for

atypical students within the framework of university elective courses and modular disciplines

Discussions

Designing didactic support for atypical students involves mastering specialized skills to model variants of didactic material, depending on the specifics of the student's inclusion. In our view, *specialized methodological skills of a foreign language teacher are the ability to transform and meaningfully apply a system of knowledge from different fields of science to solve methodological problems of foreign language education in the context of the implementation of inclusive practices.*

The problem of designing didactic support by the future teachers of the Institute of Foreign Languages of Moscow City University lies in discovering resource opportunities of elective courses and modular disciplines for outlining Individual Educational Plan; identifying items of specialized skills of the teacher to adapt assessment materials for language and culture education, in justification of the didactic functions of technological support of atypical students; in modelling specialized skills based on the principle of personified learning and provision of high-quality education.

Conclusion

As a result, the study included a series of webinars devoted to the development of didactic tools for inclusive teaching foreign languages, a forum for parents "Specifics of socialization of schoolchildren with problems with learning and upbringing", a round table discussion "Technologies of socialization of schoolchildren with problems in education", an interactive class "Formation of foreign language lexical and grammatical skills of the blind and visually impaired". Practical students' outcomes were presented at the international scientific and practical conference "Inclusive Foreign Language Education Today: problems and solutions" with 203 speeches during 2017-2020.

The results of an experimental step-by-step study of the problem of building specialized teacher's skills to design author's didactic materials as a supplement to modern foreign language textbooks prove that it is a top relevant issue of modern Russian education. Designing a didactic support for atypical students in the conditions of personalized learning and upbringing shows that during a one term course of training there is a progress in the skills formation, but this process must be consolidated at the further stages of teacher training: 1) it is necessary to develop these skills in the next courses of study in the form of other modules of additional education; 2) it is necessary to design professional development programs for teachers, taking into account various learning opportunities; 3) introduce a model for designing didactic support for atypical students in the practice of teaching, not only in the context of foreign language teaching in secondary

school, but also at other levels of education.

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